

ISic2898

I.Sicily inscription 2898

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (local: riolite bianco-grigiastra)

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Contr. Diana, sporadic find

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 13488

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334641

1. [— — —]νας

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645291

PHI 334641

Bibliography

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le

iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 537
Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M. 1994. Meligunis Lipara VII. Lipari. Contrada
Diana. Scavo XXXVI in proprieta Zagami (1975-1984). Palermo. At no.124 pl.136

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